

Research paper

Correlations between bulk and surface properties of meibomian lipids with alteration of wax-to-sterol esters content

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ABSTRACT

In a recent study (Ewurum et al., 2021), wax (WE) and sterol esters (CE) from human meibum secretions (MGS) were separated and reconstituted with controlled WE/CE ratios (0%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 75% and 100% CE weight fractions). It was found that the alterations in the CE content of WE/CE mixtures modified the hydrocarbon chain conformation and packing of the mixture. A major question that emerges is whether the spectroscopic packing parameters determined for bulk meibum translate to a change in the performance of meibomian layers at the air/water interface, as it is the surface film functionality that is crucial for the performance of MGS at the ocular surface. The study of human meibum films with Langmuir surface balance was performed to access the surface properties at blink-like deformations of the film area. Surface pressure (π)-area (A) isocycles and stress relaxations were used to assess the layer's reorganization during area cycling and dilatational elasticity, respectively. The morphology of the films was monitored by Brewster angle microscopy. It was found that the increased order and chain melting temperature of the bulk samples correlated with a raise in the maximum surface pressure attained at minimal surface area and in the transient dilatational modulus of the meibomian layers. Such correlations may allow for development of an improved understanding between the bulk and surface properties of human meibum and of other natural and synthetic tear lipid films.

1. Introduction

The tear film lipid layer (TFLL) that stabilizes the air/ aqueous tear (AT) interface of the tear film (TF) in an open eye, represents an amalgam of 236 lipid species distributed among nine molecular classes (Willcox et al., 2017b, Georgiev et al., 2017, Brown et al., 2013, Borchman et al., 2011). It is built primarily (> 95%) by the meibomian gland secretion (MGS, or simply meibum) with the putative minor inclusions of phospholipids released from the lacrimal glands (Willcox et al., 2017a, Georgiev et al., 2017, Borchman et al., 2011). MGS is a composite lipid-rich mixture that may also contain up to 22 wt% non-lipid components (proteins, salts, polysaccharides) (McMahon et al., 2013, Butovich, 2013, Borchman et al., 2011). Meibomian lipids are composed of > 90% non-polar lipids (NPL, primarily wax esters (WE), cholesteryl esters (CE), and triacylglycerides) and < 10% polar amphiphilic lipids (phospholipids and (O-acyl)- ω -hydroxy fatty acids)

(Butovich, 2013, Borchman et al., 2011). MGS was found to form a 16–170 nm thick viscoelastic duplex film composed of a monomolecular layer of amphiphilic polar lipids at the aqueous interface and a NPL stratum of generally unstructured lipophilic suspension situated on top and facing the air (Georgiev et al., 2014, Rosenfeld et al., 2013). Recently, it became clear that the quantitative or qualitative abnormalities of TFLL, commonly referred as meibomian gland disease (MGD), represent the leading cause of dry eye syndrome (DES) and affect up to 86% of all patients with DES. Caused by everyday influences like contact lens wear and extended staring at a computer screen, DES (characterized by TF instability, visual disturbances and chronic eye pain) is today's major ophthalmic public health disease, affecting the quality of life of 10–30% of the human population worldwide and exerting gross socioeconomic impact on modern society (McDonald et al., 2016, Donthineni et al., 2019).

CE and WE make up ~80% of human meibum (Butovich, 2013,

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Fig. 1. Curve fit of the ^1H NMR spectrum of the enriched wax fraction of meibum from a 67 year-old donor. The areas of the fitted curves were used to determine the hydrocarbon chain branching according to Borchman and Ramasubramanian, 2019. The original spectrum appears above the fitted resonances.

Borchman et al., 2011). This is very interesting as the combination of WE and CE and the balance between the two is found to be critical for the functionality of multiple biological coatings and surfaces like human skin sebum, cuticle of plants, the spermaceti of whales, and the exoskeleton coating of insects (Dyas and Goad, 1993, Koopman, 2018, Sharma et al., 2018, Katz, 1981). Therefore the maintenance of the ratio of CE/WE in human tear lipids may be important to tear film stability and the prevention of dry eye. However, the interaction between the native WE and CE remains almost unstudied.

The key to understanding how CE and WE are involved in natural and pathological processes is to elucidate the compositional, structural and functional relationships of these lipids. In the context of TFL lipidomic studies, two populations of donors have been observed, with lower and higher ratios of CE/WE [15–18]. The CE/WE ratio has been shown to decrease in patients with meibomian gland dysfunction (Borchman et al., 2019, Hetman and Borchman, 2020) and increase between birth and 19 years of age (Borchman et al., 2013, 2019). It is unclear whether changes in CE/WE ratio are directly related to tear film (in)stability in health and disease or is a marker for and/or contributes to dry eye disease. Nor is it known how CE influences the structure and function of meibomian surface films. Model studies using synthetic CE and WE (Hetman and Borchman, 2020, Borchman et al., 2013) have provided some insight, however, the extrapolation of these results to human meibum is limited as meibomian CE and WE contain variable amounts of hydrocarbon chain branching, saturation and chain length (Butovich, 2009, Chen and Nichols, 2018, Nicolaides et al., 1981) and the synthetic lipids do not. Hydrocarbon chain branching, saturation and chain length could influence the conformation and the structure of the lipids. As almost all the WE and CE moieties found in human meibum cannot be purchased and have not been synthesized, it is almost impossible to model the diverse composition of the MGS lipids using synthetic WE and CE. In a recent study (Ewurum et al., 2021) we managed to circumvent these complexity issues by demonstrating that WE and CE from the meibomian glands could be separated from each other using MgO column chromatography. ^1H NMR and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analyses of bulk meibomian samples with controlled WE/CE ratios revealed that changes in the WE/CE ratio undoubtedly modifies the hydrocarbon chain conformation and packing of

MGS lipids. The direction of the change in the order parameter and the phase transition temperature of the mixtures with the alteration of the samples' WE/CE ratio depended on whether CE or WE were the more ordered of the two ester fractions, a phenomenon that is supposed to depend on the age of the individual as was indeed the case in our study. It was shown that the degree of miscibility between the lipid species was significantly influenced by the CE/WE relative content.

A major question that emerges is whether the spectroscopic parameters determined for bulk meibum samples translate to a notable change into the performance of meibomian layers at the air/water interface as it is the surface film functionality that is crucial for the MGS performance *in vivo* at the ocular surface. In order to answer this question, the meibum samples with controlled CE/WE ratios (0%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 75% and 100% CE) analyzed in our previous study were used to form films at the air/water surface of a Langmuir trough. The study of human meibum films with a Langmuir surface balance allows one to access the surface properties of the sample at blink-like deformations of film area and has proven to be a way to study tear lipids' interfacial properties at physiologically relevant deformation regimes under controlled conditions (Georgiev et al., 2017). Surface pressure (π)-area (A) isocycles and stress relaxations were used to assess the layer's reorganization during area cycling and dilatational elasticity respectively. Film morphology was monitored by Brewster angle microscopy (BAM). To determine the relationship between the bulk and surface properties of meibum samples over a range of CE/WE ratios, the correlation between the spectroscopic and surface film parameters were examined. Such correlations improve our understanding of the relationships between the bulk and surface properties of human meibum and of natural and synthetic tear lipid films.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Written consents were obtained from two volunteers, and all protocols were in accordance with the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. Protocols and procedures for the current retrospective study were approved by the University of Louisville Institutional Review Board (#

11.0319, August 2016). The donors did not complain of dry eye disease and their meibomian gland orifices showed no evidence of keratinization or plugging with turbid or thickened secretions, and no dilated blood vessels were observed on the eyelid margin. Meibum collection was done by medically qualified personnel using an ILUX instrument (Alcon, Fort Worth, TX) as previously described (Ewurum et al., 2021). The procedures of purification of meibomian WE and CE as well as the realization of specific CE/WE ratios (0%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 75% and 100% mole fractions of CE) are described there as well (Ewurum et al., 2021).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Spectroscopy

2.2.1.1. NMR spectroscopy. ^1H NMR spectra from a Varian Inova 700 MHz NMR spectrometer were used to confirm the presence of meibum CE or WE in separated fractions, and to measure hydrocarbon chain branching, saturation, molar ratios of CE to WE, and mole percent amount of pooled CE and WE. Samples were dissolved in 600 μL of CDCl_3 . The following resonances were used for hydrocarbon chain compositional quantification: 5.32–5.35 ppm for the total double bonds, 0.66 ppm and 1.0 ppm resonances for CE and 4.0 ppm for WE. GRAMS/386 software (Galactic Industries, Salem, NH) was used to analyze all spectra. Hydrocarbon chain branching was measured by curve fitting the CH_3 resonance region as described (Borchman et al., 2019). A typical curve fit for the wax ester from the older donor is shown in Fig. 1. The areas of the fitted curves were used to determine the hydrocarbon chain branching. Resonance assignments for this region can be found in (Borchman et al., 2019).

2.2.1.2. FTIR spectroscopy. A Fourier Transform infrared spectrometer (Nicolet 5000 Magna Series; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc., Waltham MA) was used to determine the effect of temperature on driving meibum lipids to transform from a predominantly ordered phase to a substantially disordered phase. The spectrometer was equipped with a temperature-recording thermistor and a water bath that regulated the temperature of the jacketed sample cell. Spectral symmetric CH_2 stretching band near 2850 cm^{-1} ($\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$) after baselining, was used to estimate the content of *trans* and *gauche* rotamers in the hydrocarbon chains. The change in $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ versus temperature was employed in characterizing lipid phase transitions as described previously (Ewurum et al., 2021, Borchman et al., 2007b) and thus lipid order at $33.4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was calculated by extrapolating the $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ at $33.4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $36\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ from the fit of the phase transition and then using percent *trans* rotamer as a refashioned parameter for $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$, and an index for lipid fluidity (Borchman et al., 1991). All phase transitions were fit into a two-state sigmoidal equation (Eq. 1) using Sigma plot 10 software (Systat Software, Inc. Chicago IL):

$$\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}} = (\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}})_{\text{minimum}} + ((\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}})_{\text{maximum}} - (\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}})_{\text{minimum}}) / (1 + (\text{temperature} / \text{Tc})^{\text{hillslope}}) \quad (1)$$

$\tilde{\nu}_{\text{sym}}$ is the frequency of the symmetric CH_2 stretching band near 2850 cm^{-1} . Tc is the phase transition temperature (Ewurum et al., 2021, Borchman et al., 2007b).

Phase transition temperature (Tc), an indicator for the melting of half of sample lipid molecules, was measured at the inflection point of the sigmoidal function. Enthalpy and entropy changes were calculated from the slopes of Arrhenius kinetics plots, using the calculated percentage of *trans* rotamers. The CH_2 moieties of the hydrocarbon side chains of lipids are expected to exhibit a higher vibrational frequency with an increase in entropy due to melting. Maximum and minimum frequencies were indicative of the most ordered and least ordered conformations, respectively. Cooperativity was monitored by the broadness of the phase transition function as an indication of the degree to which a lipid influences the melting or ordering of adjacent lipids. GRAMS/386 software (Galactic Industries, Salem, NH) was used for initial FTIR spectra collection while Sigma plot 10 software (Systat Software, Inc. Chicago IL) was utilized to compute phase transition data.

2.2.2. Langmuir surface balance studies

Surface pressure/area (π -A) isotherms were measured (Georgiev et al., 2014) by Langmuir surface balance μ Trough XS, area 135 cm^2 , volume 100 mL (Kibron, Helsinki, Finland), via the Wilhelmy wire probe method (instrumental accuracy 0.01 mN/m). Physiological saline solution buffer (PBS, pH 7.4) was utilized as trough subphase. A micro-syringe (Hamilton Co., Reno, NV, USA) was used to uniformly spread human MGS (18 μL of 1 mg/mL chloroform solution) over the air/saline surface. The trough was fitted under an acrylic cover to protect the surface from dust and to suppress the PBS subphase evaporation (90% relative humidity is maintained under the cover). After 15 min were provided for chloroform evaporation, film compression was initiated by two symmetrically moving barriers. Dynamic compression–expansion isocycling of the film area was performed at the maximum barrier's rate (70 mm/min), at which there was no leakage of the film. Ten consecutive cycles were performed with each film studied. Typically, after the third cycle, the π (A) curves attained constant shape and those π (A) isotherms were analyzed further. All isotherms were repeated at least in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. The experiments were performed at $35\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, i.e., the physiological temperature of the ocular surface. The films' morphology was monitored by a Brewster angle microscope (MC-BAM, Imperx, Boca Raton, Florida, USA).

Film in-plane elasticity (or rigidity) modulus, Cs^{-1} , at a given surface pressure was calculated from π /A compression isotherms using the equation (Davies and Rideal, 1961, Telesford et al., 2015):

$$\text{Cs}^{-1} = -A_{\pi} (d\pi/dA)_{\Gamma} \quad (2)$$

where A_{π} is the area at the indicated π . The inflexion points in the π/Cs^{-1}

Table 1
Structural and spectroscopic parameters of wax and sterol esters of human meibum samples.

Parameters	66 y.o. donor			29 y.o. donor		
	WE	CE	P, CE vs WE	WE	CE	P, CE vs WE
Anteiso branched, %	8	3	< 0.05	18	15	< 0.05
Straight chain, %	74	88	< 0.05	79	79	> 0.05
Iso branched, %	18	9	< 0.05	3	6	< 0.05
Branched, %	26	12	< 0.05	21	21	> 0.05
Transition temperature, $^\circ\text{C}$	32.3 ± 0.4	26.4 ± 0.8	< 0.0001	33.9 ± 0.3	37.1 ± 0.3	< 0.0001
Cooperativity (Hill coefficient)	5.8 ± 0.3	5.7 ± 0.9	> 0.5	8.9 ± 0.6	7.3 ± 0.4	0.037
Order 36°C , % <i>trans</i>	38.0 ± 0.7	32.7 ± 2	0.02	43.2 ± 0.9	57.8 ± 1.2	< 0.0001
Order 33.4°C , % <i>trans</i>	44.5 ± 0.7	36.3 ± 2.5	0.005	54.2 ± 0.9	67.8 ± 1.2	< 0.0001
Δ enthalphy, kcal/mol	135 ± 5	122 ± 5	> 0.5	186 ± 7	172 ± 8	> 0.5
Δ entropy, kcal/mol	0.44 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.02	> 0.5	0.61 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.03	> 0.5
Minimum Frequency, cm^{-1}	2849.54 ± 0.05	2849.2 ± 0.2	> 0.5	2848.84 ± 0.06	2848.67 ± 0.05	> 0.5
Maximum Frequency, cm^{-1}	2854.19 ± 0.08	2853.6 ± 0.2	0.012	2853.88 ± 0.09	2854.34 ± 0.06	0.0003

Fig. 2. Surface pressure/area isotherms (red curves) and surface pressure/in-plane reciprocal compressibility modulus (blue curves) of meibomian films from a 66 years old donor with different WE/CE ratios. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Surface pressure/area isotherms (red curves) and surface pressure/in-plane reciprocal compressibility modulus (blue curves) of meibomian films from a 29 years old donor with different WE/CE ratios. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Maximum surface pressures, π_{\max} , achieved at the completion of the area compression of meibomian surface layers. The π_{\max} values are averaged from $n = 3$ measurements.

dependencies indicate the surface pressures at which significant reorganization of the surface film takes place in the course of the film compression. According to the Davies and Rideal (Davies and Rideal, 1961) criterion, for $C_S^{-1} < 50$ mN/m the state of a given monolayer is classified as liquid expanded (LE), for $50 < C_S^{-1} < 250$ mN/m the state is liquid condensed (LC), for $C_S^{-1} > 250$ mN/m the monolayer is described as solid state. Another parameter that was extracted by the compression isotherms is the maximum surface pressure value, π_{\max} , attained at the minimal film area which is proportional to the maximum lateral packing density that can be reached by the meibomian films at blink like deformation (Ivanova et al., 2015).

The transient dilatational viscoelasticity of meibum films was also accessed by measurement of the surface pressure relaxation transients after a small rapid compression step was applied to the layers (Nencheva et al., 2018, Loglio et al., 1986, Monroy et al., 1998). First, the film was compressed and allowed to equilibrate at initial surface pressure, $\pi_0 = 15$ mN/m. Then, the film was instantaneously contracted with a small compression step, $\Delta A/A_0 = 5\% \pm 1\%$ (A_0 is initial film area, and ΔA is area change). The transient elasticity modulus was calculated as:

$$E(t) = -A_0(d\pi(t)/dA) \quad (3)$$

where $d\pi(t)$ is the transient surface pressure difference at any moment of

Fig. 5. BAM micrographs (500 $\mu\text{m} \times 300 \mu\text{m}$) of meibomian surface films. The morphologies were not sensitive to the individual WE/CE ratios of the samples and instead displayed similar appearances for wide range of CE weight fractions. The characteristic pattern is confirmed that at lower surface pressures the meibomian films contained some thinner (presumably monolayer) stripes, which disappeared at further compression when continuous thick duplex film is formed (see main text for details).

Fig. 6. Upper row: Stress relaxation transients of meibomian layers formed by samples from 66 y.o. and 29 y.o. donor at different CE weight fractions. Bottom row: The left panel shows the fit ($R^2 > 0.95$) of Eq. 3 (in the main text) to a relaxation transient. The right panel illustrates the Maxwell viscoelastic model of parallel dashpots and spring (the spring corresponds to the E_{∞} term in Eq. 3).

the relaxation t .

3. Results

3.1. Compositional and spectroscopic characteristics of the meibomian samples

The main compositional characteristics of the samples studied are shown in Table 1.

The data summarize the WE/CE weight % ratio and the molar % of CE of the meibomian samples obtained from the two donors after the separation of the two esters fraction and the subsequent reconstitution of MGS compositions at various WE/CE ratios.

The comparison of the average (between the old and young donor) values of the % of straight and branched (anteiso and iso-) WE and CE of the native samples is in good agreement with previously published estimates about the average composition of meibomian lipids (Butovich et al., 2016, Nicolaidis, 1970). Direct comparison between the fluidity of WE and CE fractions from younger and the older donor through the parameters summarized in Table 1 can be made based on the order of the fractions at 33.4°C and 36°C as well as on the transition temperatures. It can be seen that for the 66 y.o. donor WE is more ordered than CE at both temperatures (44.5 ± 0.7 vs $36.3 \pm 2.5\%$ trans and 38.0 ± 0.7 vs $32.7 \pm 2\%$ trans at 33.4°C and 36°C) while for the 29 y.o. donor it is the other way around (CE displayed >1.25 higher order than WE for both temperatures). Similarly the phase transition temperature of WE (32.3 ± 0.4 °C) is higher than the one of CE (26.4 ± 0.8 °C) for the 66 y.o. o. samples but WE melts at lower temperature than CE for the 29 y.o. donor specimens (33.9 °C vs 37.1 °C for WE and CE respectively). Thus CE fraction is more fluid than WE for the older donor and CE is less fluid than the WE for the younger donor MGS. This observation is in agreement with previous assumptions about the changes in human meibum

Table 2

Fitting parameters of Eq. (3) to stress relaxation transients of the meibomian layers studied. For all systems $R^2 \geq 0.95$.

System	E_{∞} , mN/m	A_1 , mN/m	τ_1 , s	A_2 , mN/m	τ_2 , s
66 y.o, 0% CE	51.6	2.72	5	20.97	52.76
66 y.o, 20% CE	33	7.71	3	22.93	125.18
66 y.o, 30% CE	33.8	5.23	1	27.68	85.93
66 y.o, 40% CE	35.7	–	–	40.3	106.7
66 y.o, 50% CE	17	11.28	8.92	40.07	78.48
66 y.o, 75% CE	5	19.52	11.29	46.68	123.5
66 y.o, 100% CE	50	19.53	27.57	–	–
29 y.o, 0% CE	27.3	1.01	1	23.43	37.54
29 y.o, 20% CE	13.8	15.03	19.73	53.11	104.48
29 y.o, 30% CE	18	7.66	12.35	37.97	136.12
29 y.o, 40% CE	17	19.17	2	93.12	130.8
29 y.o, 50% CE	41.3	16.99	59.25	19.27	253.92
29 y.o, 75% CE	57.8	8.35	10.53	26.28	195.05
29 y.o, 100% CE	53	86.15	19.06	–	–

composition and fluidity with age and in MGD.

3.2. Surface properties of meibum samples from the two donors and different WE/CE ratios

The surface pressure/area isotherms and the dependence of in-plane elasticity (or rigidity), C_s^{-1} , of the surface films formed by the samples from the older donor are shown in Fig. 2 and from the younger donor in Fig. 3.

The surface pressure area isotherms (the red curves at Figs. 2 and 3) were used to obtain the value of the maximum surface pressure, π_{\max} , achieved at the end of compression when minimum film area was reached. It can be seen that the dependence of π_{\max} on %CE had significantly different shape for the old and for the younger donor

Fig. 7. Dependence of the plateau value E_{∞} (average of $n = 3$ replicates) of the transient dilatational elasticity modulus on the % of CE for films formed by 66 y.o. and 29 y.o. donor's meibum.

sample (Fig. 4). In the case of the older donor for the 30–80% range of CE content π_{\max} monotonously decreased, while for the younger donor, the raise of CE content up to 40% had a modest effect on π_{\max} , and at 50% CE, the maximum surface pressure rose steeply from 33 mN/m to 43 mN/m. The result corresponded well with the data (Table 1) for the older donor CE that were more fluid compared to WE and vice versa for the younger donor where WE were more fluid than CE. The π_{\max} value depends on the packing of the “end members” of the surface film. If, at the end of compression the lipid duplex film achieved a high molecular packing density, then the π_{\max} value was high. If, at the end of compression, the lipid layer was loosely packed, then the π_{\max} value decreased (Ivanova et al., 2015).

The analysis of the C_s^{-1} values (blue curves, Figs. 2 and 3) reveals that for all compositions $C_s^{-1} < 50$ mN/m i.e. according to the Davies and Rideal, (Davies and Rideal, 1961) criterion, the in-plane rigidity of the meibomian layers corresponds to the liquid extended state which agrees well with previous studies (Rosenfeld et al., 2013; Svitova et al., 2016; Nencheva et al., 2018). The inflexion points in the π/C_s^{-1} dependencies (blue curves, Figs. 2 and 3) indicate the surface pressures at which significant reorganization of the surface film takes place in the course of the film compression. It can be seen that although the behavior greatly varies between the different compositions for all the layers (both from the older and the younger donors) the inflexions occurred between 10 mN/m and 20 mN/m. Based on the BAM observations (Fig. 5) the inflexions take place when the thinner (darker) stripes, supposedly of monolayer thickness (Willcox et al., 2017b; Georgiev et al., 2017; Rosenfeld et al., 2013) within the meibum films, disappear and form thicker multilayer patches upon compression.

The data for the dilatational elasticity modulus of meibomian samples from the old and the young donor are presented in Fig. 6.

To quantify the transient behavior of the dilatational relaxation modulus, the analysis was performed via Maxwell viscoelastic model consisting of parallel Maxwell elements and a spring (Noskov et al., 2011; Loglio et al., 1986):

$$E(t) = A_i \exp \left(-\frac{t}{\tau_i} \right) + E_{\infty}, \quad (4)$$

Eq. 4 represents a sum of exponential decays with amplitude A_i and characteristic times τ_i plus plateau value E_{∞} .

The dilatational properties of both samples (from the older and from the younger donors) displayed significant similarities (Table 2). In both cases at most of the different CE contents two exponents were needed with shorter (τ_1) and longer (τ_2) characteristic relaxation times, with the weight of the slower exponent being higher than the weight of the fast one ($A_2 > A_1$). For a limited number of compositions (66 y.o. 40% CE, 66 y.o. 100% CE and 29 y.o. 100% CE) a single exponent was sufficient to describe the relaxation transients.

From the relaxation transients the plateau values, E_{∞} of the

dilatational elasticity modulus was determined from the relaxation tails and plotted as function of the % CE (Fig. 7). The dependence of E_{∞} and π_{\max} on % CE had a similar shape for the older and younger donors. In the case of the older donor, for 30–80% CE, the value of E_{∞} monotonously decreased, while for the younger donor the increase of up to 40% CE had a moderate effect on E_{∞} and at 50% CE, the E_{∞} increased steeply from 18 mN/m to 41 mN/m. Again, this behavior agrees well with the results (Table 2) for the older donor CE that was more fluid compared to WE and vice versa for the younger donor where WE were more fluid than CE. Similar to π_{\max} , the E_{∞} value reflected the capability of the molecules in the surface films to maintain high molecular packing density at the aqueous surface and to store (instead of dissipate) the energy put into the layer by the rapid step deformation.

As a final step, the correlation (Fig. 8) between the mean values of the two surface film parameters, π_{\max} and E_{∞} , and of the bulk spectroscopic parameters obtained for the meibum samples, hydrocarbon chain order (HCO) and transition temperature (T_c) was determined. For the samples from both donors surface chemistry parameters correlated with the spectroscopic parameters (Fig. 8).

4. Discussion

A major finding of the current study is that enriched native CE can influence both the bulk and the surface properties of enriched native WE with the nature of the change dependent on whether the CE is more or less ordered than WE. Many of the spectroscopic parameters (Table 1) were different between WE from older and younger donor and also between CE of older and younger donor. As studies of purified WE and CE from meibum have never been performed, what the normal variation between these properties in the general human population can be revealed only by future studies. Future infrared spectroscopic studies involving the relationships between purified WE and CE and age, race, sex and dry eye types are needed to bridge this gap in knowledge. However, with all the inherent limitations of a case study the current findings align well with lipidomics and clinical studies of TFLL. CE/WE increases with age (Borchman et al., 2019) and CE/WE decreases with MGD (Borchman et al., 2019; Shrestha et al., 2011) yet meibum order and rigidity (as determined by IR spectroscopy) and tear film instability (determined *in vivo*) increase in both instances (Borchman, 2021). The results of the current study may provide a hint to the seemingly contradictory contribution of CE/WE to order, lipid film rigidity and tear film stability. It can be seen (Table 1) that for the older donor CE was more fluid compared to WE. For the younger donor it was just the opposite and WE was more fluid than CE. CE/WE increases with age (starting in young individuals) and CE/WE decreases with MGD (a disease more typical of the elderly population). In the light of the above, one can see that identical alterations of the CE/WE ratio in the two donors from the different age groups may have completely different

Fig. 8. Correlation between the mean values of the spectroscopic and surface film parameters of the meibomian samples from both donors. (HCO) hydrocarbon chain order; (T_c) phase transition temperature.

consequences. For the younger donor CE is more ordered than WE, and thus the raise of CE/WE ratio results in an increase of the order and packing of the binary lipid mixtures. Such phenomenon might be related with the change from thicker but more fluid lipid layer in infants, to the thinner lipid layer established in the eye of children and adults, (Sledge et al., 2017, Isenberg et al., 2003) which in turn requires a corresponding alteration in the tear lipid composition. For the older population, it might be the other way around: the CE is more fluid than WE, and therefore a lower CE/WE ratio (as in MGD) will result in an abnormally higher cohesion between the lipid molecules, and formation of abnormally rigid lipid aggregates with limited or heterogeneous spreading at the air/tear surface. The latter is among the major features of the lipid layer in MGD and may result in heterogeneous tear lipid

layer with impaired reorganization at blink and limited dilatational elasticity. Thus the outcome of an increase or a decrease in meibum CE/WE in relationship to lipid order and tear film stability depends on the changes in the relative order of CE and WE. There are number of factors that may contribute to the fluidity of CE and WE in meibum from human donors of different age groups like branching, saturation and length of the esters' acyl chains. The average hydrocarbon branching of WE and CE measured in this study agree with previous findings (Nicolaides et al., 1981, Butovich et al., 2016). It can be seen that branching cannot explain the differences in fluidity of the samples. For example the CE of 66 y.o. donor was least branched (Table 1) than all other groups and still displayed highest fluidity amongst all the ester fractions. Although such finding is in contrast to the theoretical expectations it

Fig. 9. The mixtures of wax and sterol esters (c) disrupt the tight cohesion of the pure monocomponent phases (a and b) and may result in enhanced fluidity and better spreading of the meibomian secretions.

The figure is adapted from Ewurum et al. (2021).

aligns very well with previous results (Borchman et al., 2019) that meibum of Meibomian Gland Disease (MGD) patients contained 14% less straight chains compared to MGS from healthy individuals, although MGD lipids are known to be less fluid and respectively more resistant to spreading at the ocular surface compared with “healthy” samples (Willcox et al., 2017a). Thus it appears that overall the acyl chain branching may not be crucial for MGS fluidity. Other factors that might be important are the saturation and the length of the esters’ hydrocarbons which were already shown to significantly alter MGS and tear surface properties (Nencheva et al., 2018, Georgiev et al., 2019). Although no differences between the average acyl chain length (Urata and Takaishi, 1997), hydration (Borchman et al., 2007a), and saturation (Mudgil et al., 2013, Sledge et al., 2017, Nencheva et al., 2018, Georgiev et al., 2019) of meibomian lipids with sex, race or dry eye have been reported, it is indeed possible that they could influence hydrocarbon order between WE and CE fractions of MGS. Studies to separate CE and WE from meibum are warranted to determine if/how meibum CE and WE conformation and composition change with age, gender, race and MGD and if the changes are related to tear film stability. To measure the composition of meibum using ^1H NMR and the phase transition parameters of enriched CE, enriched WE and one mixture of the two, it would take 4200 h to study 40 samples of meibum from donors of different ages, and 20 samples of meibum from donors with MGD. These extended studies, which are beyond the scope of the current pioneer work, are now underway.

An interesting question is why WE and CE often present together in nature (meibum, skin sebum, cuticle of plants, the spermaceti of whales, exoskeleton coating of insects) and how does WE influence CE hydrocarbon chain conformation and visa-versa? X-ray crystallography shows that when present alone pure WE (i.e. 0% CE) have a lamellar structure (Kreger and Schamhart, 1956, Simpson and Miwa, 1977, Weinbach et al., 1995), while pure CE (100% CE) form a smectic phase packing (Weinbach et al., 1995). Both structures (lamellar and smectic phase) when subjected to low temperatures manifest as highly ordered states with strong cohesion between the acyl chains of the molecules which will result in lack of spreading of the lipids and therefore inability to

fulfill their biological functions at the ocular surface and elsewhere. Indeed WE and CE cover external body surfaces where temperature varies widely and low temperatures are very probable. For example a recent study (Slettedal and Ringvold, 2015) showed that although in office conditions the corneal surface temperatures is around 35 °C, this value may vary greatly in the range of 25.1–42 °C depending on the ambient conditions (wind, heat etc.). Furthermore, thermal gradients on the scale of 5–6 °C were found to occur across the corneal surface even at stable ambient conditions (Schwartz and Feller, 1962; Rysä and Sarvaranta, 1974; Lorget et al., 2016). Therefore it can be hypothesized that the mixing of CE in WE results in less ordered bulk structures (Fig. 9) that will allow to balance the fluidity and order of WE/CE phases over a broad temperature range.

Another important result of the study is that some of the surface film parameters, i.e. maximum surface pressure π_{max} and the plateau value E_{∞} of the transient dilatational elasticity modulus, displayed significant correlations with the spectroscopically determined bulk properties of the meibomian samples (hydrocarbon chain order, HCO, and transition temperature, T_c). The latter observation aligns with the fact that all of these parameters indicate the capability of meibomian lipid layers to maintain dense molecular packing either in the bulk state (HCO, T_c) or in a surface film subjected to an area deformation. This is an important result as it indicates that (i) bulk properties translate to surface properties and that (ii) with the accumulation of more experimental data on a diverse set of samples from variety of donors (in terms of race, age, ethnicity, sex etc.) analytical models might be possible to predict the surface properties of tear lipids based on the spectroscopic characteristics of the samples. The physiological interpretation of the π_{max} and E_{∞} values is a complex task that requires further correlation of the *in vitro* parameters with clinical data. The maximum surface pressure, π_{max} , attained at the completion of compression was already demonstrated to be sensitive to the compositional changes of meibomian and tear surface films (Nencheva et al., 2018, Georgiev et al., 2019, Mudgil et al., 2013). Apart from, π_{max} , another parameter that has been demonstrated to strongly ($R \geq 0.9$) correlate with the bulk properties of meibomian lipids is the maximum value of the in-plane reciprocal compressibility

modulus, C_s^{-1} (Mudgil et al., 2020). Although here the correlation of the maximum C_s^{-1} with the spectroscopic parameters ($R = 0.5\text{--}0.6$; data not shown) was less pronounced further studies with higher number of samples are needed to probe for more parameters that are able to reliably detect correlations between the surface and bulk properties of meibomian lipids. Recent *in vitro* studies (Eftimov et al., 2017, Svitova and Lin, 2016) have shown that E_∞ is > 10 mN/m higher for “healthy” meibomian and tear layers compared to samples from MGD patients and from populations with increased susceptibility to dry eye. In a seminal study, (Tiffany et al., 1989) tears from donors without dry eye attained a surface pressure that was 6 ± 2.5 mN/m higher compared with tears from donors with dry eye. At the same time very high surface pressures attained at high compression are often related to strong cohesion and limited spreading of lipid films, which in turn is a symptom related to tear film instability and dry eye (Willcox et al., 2017b, Georgiev et al., 2017, Brown et al., 2013, Borchman et al., 2011). Furthermore, it is often assumed that meibum that is tightly packed, such as that from donors with dry eye due to MGD, is not fluid enough to be excreted from the meibomian gland (Butovich, 2013, Borchman et al., 2011). Thus, the delicate balance between tear lipid layer fluidity and elasticity ensure a plethora of TFL functionalities, i.e., spreading, uniform structure and dilatational elasticity and requires further studies.

5. Conclusions

Alterations in the CE content of WE/CE mixtures definitively modifies the hydrocarbon chain conformation and packing of the mixture. The direction and magnitude of the effect depends on the conformation of the WE and CE and which of the two lipid classes is more fluid than the other. Differences in the complexity of the hydrocarbon chains likely do not exert major influence on changes in the order or phase transition temperature when more ordered WE is added to less ordered CE. The alterations in the bulk properties of the lipids also influence some of the surface properties of the meibomian layers.

The major potential biological implications of our findings is that WE/CE mixtures could be advantageous in nature compared to pure WE or CE because a WE/CE mixture could be necessary in the tear film lipid layer to disrupt the ordered packing of the pure lipid species resulting in better spreading of the lipids and thus to a more stable tear film. WE may also be a necessary component of sebum, the cuticle of plants and the exoskeleton coating of insects which would be expected to fluidize pure CE allowing the mixture to spread.

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